

Supplementary figures

Fig. S1 Phylogenomic tree of *Bifidobacteriaceae*, including the names of all genera validly published under the ICNP and low-quality (LQ) MAGs from termite guts. The maximum-likelihood tree is based on an alignment of 120 single-copy marker genes generated by GTDB-Tk and was inferred with IQ-TREE under the LG+F+I+G4 model of evolution. Numbers at internal nodes indicate ultrafast bootstrap support (in percent, 1,000 replicates). MAGs with 16S rRNA genes are in red typeface, type strains of new species are printed in bold. The host families are indicated in parentheses (A, Archotermopsidae, H, Hodotermittidae; Hs, Hodotermopsidae, K, Kalotermittidae; R, Rhinotermittidae; T, Termitidae).

Fig. S2 Phylogeny of the bifunctional phosphoketolase (Xfp) of termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* (TAB) and other family members, and the homologous monofunctional phosphoketolases (Xpk) of *Actinomycetota* and other bacterial phyla. Biochemically characterized homologs (SWISS-PROT) are highlighted. The maximum-likelihood tree is based on a curated alignment of 490 amino acid positions and was inferred under the LG+G4 model of evolution. Bootstrap values were omitted for clarity.

Fig. S3 PTS systems for *N*-acetyl-glucosamine (A) and glucose/mannose (B) and their conversion to fructose 6-phosphate in termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae*.

Fig. S4 Phylogeny of the organophosphate antiporter (OPA) of termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* (TAB) and their closest relatives from public reference databases. Biochemically characterized homologs (SWISS-PROT) are highlighted. The maximum-likelihood tree is based on a curated alignment of 428 amino acid positions and was inferred under the LG+F+R9 model of evolution. Bootstrap values were omitted for clarity.

Fig. S5 Phylogeny of Group A [FeFe] hydrogenases in the genus *Ancillula* and *Opitulatrix* and their homologs in public databases. Homologs from MAGs of termite gut microbiota are marked in bold. The maximum-likelihood tree is based on a curated alignment of 281 amino acid positions and was inferred under the LG+R8 model of evolution. Numbers at internal nodes indicate ultrafast bootstrap support (1,000 replicates).

Fig. S6 Phylogeny of PFOR in termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* and their homologs from public databases. The maximum-likelihood tree is based on a curated alignment of 323 amino acid positions and was inferred under the LG+R5 model of evolution. Numbers at internal nodes indicate ultrafast bootstrap support (1,000 replicates).

Fig. S7 Enzymes of asparagine biosynthesis encoded by termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* and other family members. Abbreviations: AsnA, aspartate–ammonia ligase; AsnB, asparagine synthetase B; AspS, aspartate–tRNA ligase; GatABC, aspartyl/glutamyl-tRNA(Asn/Gln) amidotransferase.

Fig. S8 Phylogeny of the threonine/serine exporter (ThrE) of termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* and its homologs in public databases. The maximum-likelihood tree is based on a curated alignment of 259 amino acid positions and was inferred under the LG+F+R6 model of evolution. Numbers at internal nodes indicate ultrafast bootstrap support (1,000 replicates).

Fig. S9 Enzymes of murein biosynthesis encoded by termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* and other family members. Abbreviations: MurJ, Lipid II flippase; Ddl, D-alanine–D-alanine ligase; MurF, UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-tripeptide–D-alanyl-D-alanine ligase; Mpl, UDP-N-acetylmuramate–L-alanyl-gamma-D-glutamyl-meso-2,6-diaminoheptandioate ligase; MurA, UDP-N-acetylglucosamine 1-carboxyvinyltransferase; Alr, Alanine racemase; MraY, phospho-N-acetylmuramoyl pentapeptide transferase; MurB, UDP-N-acetylenolpyruvoylglucosamine reductase; FTSW, peptidoglycan glycosyltransferase.

Fig. S10 Elements of different DNA repair mechanisms encoded by *Bifidobacteriaceae* and other *Actinomycetales*.

Fig. S11 Phylogeny of the folate transporter (FolT) encoded by members of the genus *Ancillula* and its homologs from public databases. The maximum-likelihood tree is based on a curated alignment of 324 amino acid positions and was inferred under the LG+G4 model of evolution. Numbers at internal nodes indicate ultrafast bootstrap support (1,000 replicates).

Fig. S12 Expanded biosynthetic pathways for amino acid (A) and cofactor (B) biosynthesis in the *Ancillula* and *Opitulatrix* MAGs. Genes in black are encoded by both genera. Genes in purple are present only in *Ancillula*, and genes in gray are absent in both genera.

Supplementary tables

Table S1. Metagenomes of *Bifidobacteriaceae* used in this study. The accession numbers of the 16S rRNA gene sequences recovered from the datasets are indicated.

Table S2. Genome characteristics of the *Bifidobacteriaceae* genomes used in this study. The 16S rRNA gene sequences extracted from genomes are indicated.

Table S3. Analysis of the CAZymes encoded by the MAGs of termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae* with dbCAN3. Only CAZymes identified by at least two of the listed tools were included. CAZymes with signal peptides are marked in red.

Table S4. 16S rRNA gene libraries inspected for the presence of *Bifidobacteriaceae*. The accession numbers of the phylotypes recovered from the samples are indicated. For taxonomic classification and relative abundance, see Table S4.

Table S5. Relative abundance of different lineages of *Bifidobacteriaceae* in amplicon libraries of bacterial 16S rRNA gene in flagellate suspensions and whole gut samples of termites and cockroaches. Samples without *Bifidobacteriaceae* are not shown. For more information, see Table S3.

Table S6. Taxon-specific gene markers identified by CheckM v.1. in the type species of *Bifidobacteriaceae* (isolates) and the termite-specific lineages (MAGs). For an unbiased estimation of genome completeness, the gene markers that were absent from the closed genomes of all isolates (highlighted in red) were removed from the reference set.